

SURVEY OF GRAPHICAL PASSWORD

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Abstract:

Over the years security experts in the field of information technology have had a tough time to making passwords secure. Graphical passwords have been designed to try to make passwords more remarkable and more comfortable for people to use and, therefore, more secure. Passwords provide security mechanism for authentication and protection services against unwanted access to resources. A graphical based password is one promising alternatives of word-based passwords. The details of attacks and the structures of alpha numeric passwords is also compared with the graphical passwords. Human brain is good in remembering picture as compare to textual, so the graphical password having more preference in the market.

Index- Authentication, Security, Graphical passwords, Graphical passwords, authentication, persuasive technology, usable security, empirical study etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

Most ordinary authentication mechanisms include use of an alphanumeric base word that only the user to be authenticated knows and is generally delegated to as password. Philosophical conclusion of passwords can lead to the result of refining of the authentication process. The approach has infrequently been adopted in the exploration and design of computer security. Passwords too are entities having an occurrence of their own and this lead us to study them under a philosophical context [1].

Due to the difficult nature of information, be it individual information on someone's individual computer or information systems of large organizations, security is a great corner. There are three types of computer security:

- Authentication
- Authorization

- Encryption

The first and most important of these layers is authentication and it is at this layer that passwords play an important role.

Password is a confidential word or phrase that must be used to gain concession to a place. Now a days, user name and passwords are commonly used by people during a log in process that manage access to protected computer operating systems, mobile phones, cable T.V. decoders, automated teller machines(ATMs), etc. A normal computer user has passwords for many purposes: logging into accounts, regaining email, accessing applications, databases, networks, websites, an even readings the morning newspaper online. A log in window for a web site requesting a user name and password. Despite the name, there is a no need for passwords to be real words; indeed passwords which are not real words may be difficult to guess, a desirable property. Some passwords are formed from multiple words and may more correctly be called a passphrase. The term passcode is sometimes used when the confidential information is purely numeric, such as the personal identification number (PIN) commonly used for ATM access [2].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW
TYPE OF PASSWORD

Figure 1. Taxonomy of Password Authentication Techniques

There are two type of knowledge based password:

- A. ALPHANUMERIC PASSWORD
- B. GRAPHICAL PASSWORD

ALPHANUMERIC PASSWORD

Alphanumeric (sometimes shortened to **alpha metric**) is a combination of alphabetic and numeric characters, and is used to describe the collection of Latin letters and Arabic digits or a text constructed from this collection.

Merriam-Webster observes that the term "alphanumeric" may often additionally refer to other symbols, such as punctuation and mathematical symbols. In the POSIX/C locale, there are either 36 (A-Z0-9, case insensitive) or 62 (A-Za-z0-9, case-sensitive) alphanumeric characters [3].

In alpha numeric password the password are:

- It contains at least 8 characters long.
- It not associate to the user and not should easy
- It does not found in dictionary.
- Password should contain the upper and lower case[4].

GRAPHICAL PASSWORD

Graphical passwords were initially described by Blonder in 1996.

The most common computer authentication method is to use alphanumerical user names and passwords. This method has been shown to have significant drawbacks. For example, users tend to pick passwords that can be easily guessed. On the other hand, if a password is difficult to guess, then it is often difficult to remember. To address this problem, we are created authentication method that use pictures as passwords [5].

In graphical password the user can use the images as password which will produce the human friendly password that can improve the security of password from the attacker [2].

KNOWLEDGE BASED TECHNIQUES

Graphical password systems can be classified as either recognition-based (image based scheme, cued recall-based (image based scheme) or pure recall-based (grid based scheme)[3]. Graphical passwords have been proposed as alternatives to text passwords to improve both usability and security issues[6].

Recall based techniques

In which we discuss recent there types of click based graphical password techniques:

- Pass Points (PP)
- Cued Click Points (CCP)
- Persuasive Cued Click Point(PCCP)

1. Pass Points (PP)

Pass-point graphical password scheme image password consists of 5 click points on single image. For password invention user selects any pixel in the image as a click points and for login the user has to enter the same series of clicks in correct sequence within a system define tolerance square of original click points [7]. Blonder planned a graphical password scheme in that a password is created having the user click on a number of positions on an image during authentication, the user need to click on that same location where he select at time of set the graphical password. The user should be friendly with remembering the images as compare to the text. In their requirement's users must click on various items on the image in the exact location that user will select while set it. Microsoft also developed same technique of graphical password which contain only one image click point should be an only one location with three click point that same point these security system available in windows8. But details of this technique

have not been available. In pass point the predefined areas and arbitrary images are allow. To avoid the tolerance user must click on the predefined area. Image consist the many memorable points for the user. The result of graphical password showed took less attempts for the user than alphanumerical passwords. However, graphical password users had more difficulties learning the password, and took more time to input their passwords than the alphanumerical users. Again Wiedenbeck conducted a user study to evaluate the effect of tolerance of clicking during the reauthenticating stage, and the effect of image choice in the system. The result showed that memory accuracy for the graphical password was strongly reduced by using a smaller tolerance for the user clicked points, but the choices of images did not make a significant difference. The result showed that the system works for a large variety of images [8].

Figure 2.Pass Point

2. Cued Click Points (CCP)

Cued Click Points (CCP) is another type to Pass-Points. In CCP, users click one point on each of 5 images rather than on five points on one image. It provides cued-recall and introduces visual cues that without delay alert valid users if they have made a mistake when entering their latest click-point. A wrong click leads down an incorrect path, with an explicit indication of authentication failure only after the final click. Users can choose their images only to the extent that their click-point dictates the next image. If they dislike the resulting images, they could create a new password involving different click-points to get different images. For implementation, CCP initially functions like Pass-Points. During

password creation, a discretization method is used to determine a click-point's tolerance square and corresponding grid. For each click-point in a subsequent login attempt, this grid is retrieved and used to determine whether the click-point falls within tolerance of the original point. With CCP, we further need to determine which next-image to display. Using CCP as a base system, we added a persuasive feature to encourage users to select more secure passwords, and to make it more difficult to select passwords where all five click-points are hotspots. As with text passwords, Pass-Points can only safely provide feedback at the end and cannot reveal the cause of error. Providing explicit feedback in Pass-Points before the final click-point could allow Pass-Points attackers to mount an online attack to prune potential password subspaces, whereas CCP's visual cues should not help attackers in this way. Another usability improvement is that being cued to recall one point on each of five images appears easier than remembering an ordered sequence of five points on one image [9].

Figure 3:Cued Click Points System

3. Persuasive Cued Click Point(PCCP)

Persuasive technique was first discovered by Fogg as using technology to motivate and influence people to behave in a desired manner. PCCP achieves this by making the task of selecting a weak password more tedious and time consuming. The issue remain with the PCCP was shoulder surfing attack. This attack was not removed from the persuasive cued click points. The next issue remains with the persuasive cued click points, it was difficult for the user to remember the different images. It was hard for the users to remember many images for the login. As know that human can remember limited number of images.

In PCCP, user selects five images on every image the different click point is set by the user. While creation of password all image pixels get dimmed other than the small view port is randomly located on that image with fix pixels. That user need to select its click point within that random position if does not match that click point again shuffle that point still the user gate that particular selected view point. View port help users to select more random passwords that are less likely to include hotspots [9].

Davis et al. suggest that user choice in all types of graphical passwords is inadvisable due to predictability. PCCP system could influence users to select more random click-points while maintaining usability. Here the prediction of password is difficult for the attacker as password is generated in a random manner. The goal was to encourage users to behave more securely by using their own choice. In effect, behaving securely became the safe path-of-leasresistance Persuasive cued click points in which pa consists of five click-points, one on each of five images those are selected by the user. While creation of password or during registration the all part of the image get dimmed except than that the view port which is get shuffled. The user need to select their click point within the view port and they cannot be able to click anywhere outside the viewport i.e., outside the view port clicking action does not work. Viewport is nothing but a framed area. Within that random view port range there would be several tolerance squares per image or we can say tolerance area, tolerance area is nothing but the collection of all points closed to the clicked password point. If the user can't able to select the correct view port in current view image then user can press the shuffle button to repositioning the view port. User need to shuffle that view still it get its correct view port [10].

Figure 4: Persuasive Cued Click Points System

TOKEN BASED AUTHENTICATION

The Token Based Method type is again as the name suggests authentication based on a TOKEN such as: a key, a magnetic card, a smart card, a pin and an ID. If person loses a key, then user would not be able to open the security device, a person who loses his token or key would not be able to access to security device[13]. Token based authentication is based on "Something You Have" assumption[14]. Token attached or plugged into user system. Two types of token are used software and hardware token, token which connected to client system is also called software token and token which is small in size and carried out in purse or pocket[12]. This authentication is also known as two factor authentication. The weaknesses of token are, it is simple and cheap to produce, and similarly they are simple and cheap to reproduce. This makes them weak to being counterfeiting. Also, token is physical object or device, carrying them all the times is not convenient for users [7]. Most commonly used forms of two factor authentication are:

- (i) Automated Teller Machine (ATM) or Cash point Machine Card and PIN.
- (ii) Access Control Token and PIN.

In an ATM, the client puts his/her Cash point/ATM card into the ATM and the ATM requests the client to

go through his/her PIN. The information held on magnetic line of the card mutually with the PIN, encrypted data is sent to the Bank's Central Authentication method, where client entered PIN, is compared with the PIN held on file against the client bank account number and details. In this authentication scheme, user enters unique information which becomes token to access to security device.

BIOMETRIC BASED AUTHENTICATION

The Inherent Based Authentication type which is also known as Biometric Authentication [11]. Biometric based authentication involves using an access control token such as smart card, a PIN to access the smart card and a biometric value held in the central database [12]. Like token, biometric characteristic are not secret. This authentication is based on "Something You Are" assumption. It uses physiological or behavioral characteristics like fingerprint or facial scans and iris or voice recognition to recognize users are some example of biometric based authentication [11]. In this authentication, scanning device takes a user's biometric data, such as an iris pattern or fingerprint scan, and converts that biometric data into digital information a computer can understand and verify [11]. Biometric characteristics can be divided in two main classes:

A) Physiological are connected to the shape of the body and hence it varies from person to person. Some example in this case is Fingerprints, Face recognition, hand geometry and iris recognition.

B) Behavioral are related to the behavior of a person, signature, keystroke dynamics and of voice are some examples of this type of Biometric. Sometimes voice is also considered to be a physiological biometric as it varies from person to person [13]. It provides two function authentication and verification.

It is not easy to change one's fingerprint, iris or other biometric characteristics. Therefore these characteristics are permanent and not changeable [14]. It contain three mechanisms for authentication and depend on what you know (e.g.: password), what you have (e.g.: token), and who you are (e.g.: biometric), therefore it also known as Three-Factor authentication [16]. Biometric objects cannot be

stolen as tokens, keys, cards or other objects used for the conventional user verification [3]. One of the advantages of biometric authentication is their speed. Authentication by iris identification takes 2 to 3 seconds compare to authentication in token in which it take 5 to 10 second for finding key ring and locating right key.

Even the use of dead or artificial biometric characteristics should not let the attacker in. Authentication of user by iris identification takes 2 to 3 seconds than finding key ring and locating right key takes 5 to 10 seconds. Biometric identification depends on computer algorithms to make a yes/no decision. It enhances user service by providing quick and easy identification [14].

Benefits of biometric authentication:

- Highest level of protection
- Accurate and constructive recognition
- secure and user friendly

Iris technology

This recognition technique uses the iris of the eye which is colored area that surrounds the Pupil. This iris technology is unique and is obtained through video based image acquisition method. The camera is place at distance of 10 – 40 cm and it takes image in gray scale. When gray scale image is occurred then system software tries to place the iris within the image. Once an iris is found then system software creates a net of curves layer the iris. Iris code is creates depend on darkness of points all along the lines [13].

Face recognition

In recent time's facial technology developed in two areas which are Facial metric and Eigen faces. It is an application used for identifying or verifying a person from a digital image or a video frame from a video source. Facial metric technology based on particular facial appearance. The pre-defined range is set in face

region. Facial metrics are reckoned and place in face template. Template size is between 3 and 5 KB [13].

Figure5: Face recognition technique

Finger Print Technology

Fingerprints are unique and complex sufficient to provide a strong pattern for authentication. Using numerous fingerprints from the same person affords a greater degree of accuracy [17]. The usual method is uses the ink to get the finger print onto a paper. This piece of paper is then scanned using a traditional scanner. Now a days, live finger print readers are used .These are based on optical, thermal, silicon or ultrasonic principles [12].

Figure6: Fingerprint

Fingerprint technology examines by and large pattern representation on the fingerprint, all along with small special signs known as minutiae, which are the crumple endings and bifurcations or branches in the fingerprint ridges. The data remove from fingerprints are very dense and the density explains why fingerprints are a very reliable means of recognition.

COMPARISON BETWEEN TOKEN BASED AND BIOMETRIC BASED AUTHENTICATION

- Token based authentication is slow as compare to biometric authentication because authentication of user by iris recognition takes 2 to 3 seconds than finding key ring and placing right key takes 5 to 10 seconds.
- Problem with biometric authentication is if user hand or retina injures in accident then how he can access account in that point token is useful [6].
- In token data may be stolen or loss but in case of biometric psychological or behavioral characteristic of human cannot be stolen.
- Even if a token minimize the problem of identification passwords, the user must remember to carry the physical object, which is sometimes awkward as compare to biometric based authentication.

IV. ADVANTAGES OF GRAPHICAL PASSWORD

Graphical password consist set of images ,human cannot easily remember the text but image easily remember because human can friendly with images and it provide the more security than the text while any attacker try to attack it improve its security level [11].

III. OBJECTIVES

To investigate the state of the art of authentication using images (i.e. graphical passwords), To investigate the usability of available graphical methods, To develop a novel method and then evaluate its suitability as an alternative user authentication method and , To examine the use of guidance for helping users to create secure graphical secrets.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Users may find this process long and tedious. Because of this and also because most users are not familiar with the graphical passwords, they often find graphical passwords less convenient than text based passwords. Reliability The major design issue for recall-based methods is the reliability and accuracy of user input recognition. In this type of method, the error tolerances have to be set carefully – overly high tolerances may lead to many false positives while overly low tolerances may lead to many false negatives. In addition, the more error tolerant the program, the more vulnerable it is to attacks. Storage and communication Graphical passwords require much more storage space than text based passwords. Tens of thousands of pictures may have to be maintained in a centralized database. Network transfer delay is also a concern for graphical passwords, especially for recognition-based techniques in which a large number of pictures may need to be displayed for each round of verification.

V. FINDINGS

A comparison of current graphical password techniques was presented. Although the main argument for graphical passwords is that people are better at memorizing graphical passwords than text-based passwords, the existing user studies are very limited and there is not yet convincing evidence to support this argument. Their preliminary analysis suggests that it is more difficult to break graphical passwords using the traditional attack methods such as brute force search, dictionary attack or spyware. However, since there is not yet wide deployment of graphical password systems, the vulnerabilities of graphical passwords are still not fully understood. Overall, the current graphical password techniques are still immature. Much more research and user studies are needed for graphical password techniques to achieve higher levels of maturity and usefulness

VI. LIMITATIONS

In graphical password required the more database because it consist the images and as compare to text

password it required more time it means that it is time consuming than text .

The main disadvantage is that shoulder surfing i.e. while we sign in by using the graphical password the other person may be seen that after some time it may login by unauthorized user.

POSSIBLE ATTACKS ON PASSWORD

• **Brute force search:** Brute force attack is basically a global attack on passwords to search for all possible combinations of alpha numerals, in case of text-based passwords and graphical images, in case of graphical passwords. In short brute force launches attack of words that can be text-based, activity and mixed courses of action

• **Dictionary Attacks:** dictionary attack is regional attacks that run through a possible series of dictionary words, activities and mixed courses of action until one works. Even some graphical passwords are unprotected to these types of attacks. This will allow maximum sense exploitation so dictionary attacks would fail most often.

• **Shoulder surfing:** is when an attacker directly watches a user during login, or when a security camera films a user, or when an electromagnetic pulse scanner monitors the keyboard or the mouse, or when Trojan login screens capture passwords etc. [6].

• **Guessing:** is a very common problem associated with alphanumeric passwords or even graphical passwords. Guess work is possible when the domain is limited and choices are few; in other words there is a lesser utilization of senses.

• **Spy ware:** is type of malware that collects user's information about their computational behavior and personal information[18].

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this paper, various authentication scheme has been discussed which are token based and biometric based authentication. Three Factor/Biometric-based authentication techniques are suitable, safe and reliable. This system is pattern recognition system in which a person is recognized based on features derived from specific psychological or behavioral characteristics that

the person possesses, which are harder to be theft or stolen. Moreover, today's fast-paced electronic world means people are asked to remember a multitude of passwords and Personal Identification Number (PINs) for computer accounts, banks, ATMs, E-Mail, wireless, phones, websites and so forth. Biometrics holds the promise of fast, easy, accurate, reliable and less expensive authentication for a variety of application.

various authentication scheme has been discussed which have their own advantages and disadvantages. In the past conventional authentication systems were used. But as the computer increasing very rapidly, these conventional authentication systems are replaced by the other advance system like biometrics authentication system and token based authentication. In future some other important things regarding the performance of our system will be investigated like User Adoptability and Usability and Security of our system.

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